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Ways to Work as Per Plan with Group Leaders

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Annotation: *This article provides information on how a group leader can work with students according to a plan. In particular, the organization of the work of the group leader on a scientific basis, the work plan of the group leader: long-term plans, calendar plan, plan-scheme of a special educational event, advanced experience of the best group leaders, the main areas of work of the group leader, work with the group, etc. data are expressed.*

Key words: *Student, group leader, teacher, group of students, educational activities, group leader work plan, group management rules, "Group organization", "Labor education and career guidance", "Aesthetic education", such areas as "Cooperation with family and society".*

It is known that the educational process and its result depend on the level of organization of the work and its results. Only if the leader of the group can imagine the perspective to solve the educational work at the group level, he will have the ability to see the future and he will be able to work successfully.

"The 44th goal of the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the development strategy of New Uzbekistan for the years 2022-2026 is defined as follows: To improve the quality of education in schools, to bring the knowledge and skills of pedagogic personnel to the international level.

Establish local or international certification requirements for each subject for the school to operate.

Diagnostics of the knowledge and skills of school teachers who do not have a category.

To continue filling general education schools, especially educational institutions in remote areas, with highly educated pedagogic personnel.

Further improvement of the system of appointing the principal and his deputies in schools, taking into account ensuring the participation of school teachers and parents.

Optimizing the activities of district departments of the public education system due to full digitization."

Nowadays, the organization of work on a scientific basis has become an important demand of the time. Therefore, the group leader must comply with the following requirements when organizing his work on a scientific basis:

- determine a specific goal that is important for this day in his work;
- taking into account the general goal of education;
- explanation of the tasks given to them based on the nature of the group of students;
- knowledge of the general principles and laws of education;
- to know well the form, method and means of influencing students;
- Should know the rules of managing a student group and the laws of team development.

We know that it is impossible to work in education without creativity. If the leader of the group knows well the pedagogical meaning of each step in his work, he will become an engineer of the students' hearts, otherwise he will remain an ordinary craftsman.

Education as the main object of pedagogy has been the center of attention of scientists throughout the history of the development of pedagogy. At the same time, the meaning of the concept of "education" is of practical importance. Because this concept determines the main approaches to the tasks and goals of pedagogical activity.

By education, we understand the formation of personal, moral qualities in the person being formed. Being closely connected with education, upbringing also has its own laws. Education is a single process. But they are not exactly alike. The unity of education and training lies primarily in the commonality of their purpose.

General secondary (eleven years of education), secondary special (nine years of basic secondary and two years of secondary special education), primary professional education (full persons who have received nine years of basic secondary and two years of primary professional education), as well as secondary special, vocational education (nine years of general secondary and three years of Persons who have received secondary special, vocational education) have the right to receive higher education.

In recent years, the needs of students and the range of students have grown and changed immeasurably. Science and technology news, scientific popular books, youth technical and artistic magazines, films and readers are introduced to rich resources. If the group leader's work in the group is not worthy of the level of the students' needs arising from this information, then copying and formality will occur in the work, and the interest in the work organized by the group leader will lag behind the growth of the students. Therefore, when planning his work, the leader of the group should take into account the level of development of students, their needs, the stages of community development, the activity and opportunities of the youth organization.

For this, the group leader's work plan:

Firstly, according to its content, it should be oriented to the ideological-political, socially useful direction, that is, it should pay special attention to the work aimed at the benefit of society and others;

Secondly, to choose the direction of education, the means of influencing students in accordance with the purpose, that is, to determine what and to whom the planned activities are aimed;

Thirdly, the tasks in the plan should be clearly indicated by the executors, time, and form of work for a specific common goal;

Fourthly, the activities in the plan correspond to the students' abilities and age;

Fifth, based on students' interest and needs;

Sixth, taking into account the participation of the whole team and individual students in the performance of the tasks;

Seventh, all the work that needs to be done must meet the requirements of informing everyone in advance.

In the experiment, the three different plans of the group leader are:

1. Prospective plans (designed for the long term and at the same time serving as a general program for educating the group and each person in it);
2. A calendar plan (usually drawn up for a month and showing specific tasks for each day of this month);
3. A plan drawn up for a separate educational event is a synopsis (sometimes it is also called a scenario of an educational event).

No matter what the plan is, it is necessary to reflect the content of the educational activity and the development perspective of the group of students.

"According to Appendix 1 of the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-158 dated September 11, 2023, "Uzbekistan - 2030 Strategy" in item I of the performance indicators of the goals to be achieved by 2030: "Educational System Reforms" in "Creating suitable conditions for their development" 1.1. In part "Improving the status of pedagogic personnel, aligning their knowledge and qualifications with international standards", the following was determined:

1. Sending 1,000 educators and teachers to foreign countries for training and internship.
2. Double the average salary of teachers of pre-school educational organizations and general secondary educational institutions.
3. Continuous training of 500,000 employees of pre-school educational organizations and general secondary educational institutions.
4. Introduction of a system of training of personnel in the areas of pedagogical education for applicants in high-need areas and remote areas on the basis of a full state grant.

Based on the experience of the best team leaders, approximate plans that reflect the following directions are recommended below:

1. The main directions of the group leader's work with the group: "Organization of the group", "Labor education and guidance for choosing a profession", "Aesthetic education", "Cooperation with the family and the public" includes

Forming a group - this involves the provision of pedagogical guidance for self-management of students. For this purpose, the agenda of the group meetings, their preparation and holding, and work with activists are provided.

Vocational education and guidance for choosing a profession - rational organization of study and educational work for students, as well as self-service, socially useful work, technical invention, organization of career choice. events are shown.

Teachers who teach different subjects study children's interests and involve them in various clubs and activities. Various educational events and competitions are held at the school. In conducting these events, they use the help of parents and former students, invite famous people to the school. The main socializing factor of school-aged children is the peer group that forms the children's subculture. A social pedagogue should know the tasks of these phenomena, and be able to see their place in the development of personal qualities and social relations of students.

Evenings, mornings, book readers' conference, conducting interviews, discussing films and performances, amateur singing and art reading contests, viewing paintings, going to museums and exhibitions, "students and youth music" week, going to the cinema, theaters, all this is the content of the direction of aesthetic education.

Also, involving teachers teaching in the group in group educational work, conducting additional classes for students, science and creative circles, discussions, scientific conferences, interesting meetings, science weeks. will be lit.

Working with the family and the community - activities aimed at developing the moral requirements for the family and the students of the educational institution are shown. In this, it is determined how parents and the public will help in organizing the life and activities of the group. At the same time, parents' meetings and conversations organized for parents, the topics of lecture conferences, who will go to the family and a number of other things will be determined. In particular, it is necessary to pay special attention to cooperation with the public, in particular, to production enterprises, to determining the ways and form of involving them in the life of the group.

It is not necessary to show many activities in each direction in the planning. Because each event always solves several educational tasks. The success of the work is not determined by the amount of activities, but by the level, quality and system of educational influence on students, as well as life experiences. The plan can be weekly, monthly, quarterly, half-yearly, yearly.

It is useful for the leader of the group to use whatever is convenient for him. The teacher's plan is made in one copy and is kept by him (group leader) after approval by the director.

A plan is a program of action, and a schedule is drawn up to ensure its implementation. The calendar is intended for a quarter, often a month. In order for it to be clear and to ensure the implementation of plans, the head of the group should fully take into account the traditional work that may take place at the level of the educational institution during this period. For example, there are traditional events such as "Knowledge Day", "Last Call Day", "Youth Day", "Teacher's Day" associated with the beginning of the school year in September. Also, the last Friday of every month was announced as "Spirituality and Enlightenment Day" at the school, and it has become a tradition. On this day, conversations between groups, competitions, poetry evenings, meetings and other events are held. In this case, separate weeks or ten days are dedicated to a certain field, in particular, art week, technical creativity, science week, labor week, sports ten days.

It is good and useful to book the days of the week according to the psychological possibilities, for example, Monday is more difficult, plan bright, emotionally powerful work on this day (holiday meetings, publication of competition results, etc.), Saturday is more lazy. 'tadi, because as the week ends, fatigue increases, so it is useful to plan things that will give it refreshment and cheerfulness.

The season also affects the schedule. For example, on warm autumn, sunny spring days, it is advisable to organize games and work-related activities in the open air, and to use more oral forms of work (they take place indoors) on rainy and frosty days.

The use of forms of work such as circle work, gatherings and meetings, conversations and lectures, discussion and political information in the middle days of the week is the same term. The calendar has a lot of space for traditional activities. Usually, we come across cases where they are always the same. These activities have become so popular that they often leave students feeling disillusioned and disinterested. For example, the celebration of "Independence Day" and the holding of an educational event related to "Knowledge Day" all consist of a ceremonial, artistic and public part. It is required that the group leader formulates this based on a plan in advance, creates a scenario, and effectively uses all the necessary tools.

Therefore, if the leader of the group organizes the activities for various educational activities organized in the educational institution every year with a new content and changes it from year to year, then the activity of the students will increase, and they will be encouraged to take initiative. said. For example, if in the first year, a holiday party is planned for "Defenders of the Fatherland Day", in the second year, the laying of wreaths at the "Mourning Mother" statue, and in the next year, a series of sports competitions in shooting, aiming, and overcoming an obstacle are included in the plan, and it will be varied in terms of content. During the preparation for these works, it would be appropriate if watching artistic and popular films, discussing them, listening to our national tunes and songs, and announcing the competition of brush lovers would also take place in the plan. If one of these works is selected and included in the calendar every year, the result will be good.

When several parallel groups participate in group activities in the group leader's plan, combining forces saves time and effort. The group activity chosen by the group leader is effective if it is subordinated to a specific goal. For example, the formation of the "Youth Union" organization depends on the ability of the group leader to provide leadership and organizational opportunities for new members, to organize the youth to do something and teach others in the community organization, and to take care of them to create the traditions of the group. 'liq. It is a requirement of the time that the plan reflects specific work forms that serve this purpose.

The calendar plan of the group leader can be in the following diagram. This work we have cited is tentative. However, he can be an example for each group leader in planning and analyzing his work according to the conditions and opportunities of his group.

In conclusion, we can note that it is advisable for the group leader to make a plan for himself for a week. The plan should show the daily, weekly and monthly work content of the team leader. The leader of the group is required to clearly define his work plans in accordance with the events and incidents that occur in the life of the group, in the school, in social life, and according to the needs and necessities that have arisen by chance, and accordingly carry out his work on time.

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